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PRESILIENT

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Comparative Horizon Scanning Report

Informality and innovation: building post-pandemic resilient communities in Kenya.

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0. Executive Summary

This report is the result of a Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise conducted within the PRESILIENT project with the aim of investigating the role of the informal economy in building post-pandemic resilience in the Global South. The HS activity aimed to identify economic sectors most affected by the COVID-19 crisis, as well as those showing signs of adaptation, innovation, and recovery, with a particular focus on informal economic dynamics.

This Kenya-focused report draws on qualitative and desk-based methods, including literature review, policy and media analysis, and grey literature, to investigate emerging socio-economic and political-economic trends in the country's informal sector. The results suggest that scholars, policy makers and practitioners in Kenya focused mostly on COVID-related impacts on health sector, social protection, digital labor platforms, tourism and agricultural sector. These topics aligned with Kenya socio economic needs, especially in managing the impacts of the pandemic, supporting informal economic structures, and leveraging digital innovations. Conversely, topics like waste management and urban settlement were lower in priority, possibly due to other pressing issues taking precedence.

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- **Keywords**

Informal sector, Covid-19, Post-pandemic recovery, Shadow economy, Innovation, Small business, Regulation, Micro insurance, Inclusive finance, Social protection, Microfinance, Savings groups, Informal finance, Informal settlement, Health insurance, Education, Kenya, Mobile money, Digital platform, Technology acceptance, Financial inclusion, Digital divide, Digital literacy, Resilience

1. Introduction

This document is part of the PRESILIENT project's WP1 deliverables and presents the Kenyan country-level contribution to the Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise. The Horizon Scanning methodology, as defined in the PRESILIENT Global Research Protocol, is a collective and comparative tool used to identify early signals, opportunities, and risks that may shape the future of informal economies in the Global South. The overarching aim is to trace which sectors declined or expanded in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and to identify those that could contribute to resilient and inclusive post-pandemic recovery pathways.

The HS exercise across PRESILIENT's 15-country network was designed to be flexible and adapted to the specificity of each context. While the general methodological protocol outlined the use of mixed methods and potential integration of bibliometric and quantitative trend analyses, each Early Stage Researcher (ESR) was also encouraged to adapt the tools according to their disciplinary background and access to sources. In this case, the report builds on a quantitative and qualitative analysis, focusing on sectoral fluctuations and also on how local actors interpret, resist, or creatively adapt to structural pressures.

In this Kenyan case, no large-scale statistical dataset or automated bibliometric analysis was used. Instead, the methodological approach focused on:

- A thematic review of literature, reports, and critical essays related to informality, livelihoods, and resilience in Kenya.
- Analysis of grey literature, policy documents, and national and international development discourse.
- A comparative reading of media narratives and regional reports, actively including sources coming from non-conventional and independent media, which are often more attuned to grassroots perspectives and less filtered by institutional agendas.
- Engagement with experts and critical development studies addressing indigenous and community-based economies.

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This interpretive and grounded approach is consistent with PRESILIENT’s epistemological stance, which doesn’t reduce informality to a statistical anomaly to be corrected, recognizing it instead as a field of knowledge, agency, and innovation. As such, the report highlights the political and ethical dimensions of economic practices, where the informal economy is often tied to broader struggles for autonomy, dignity, global justice, and environmental sustainability. In this context, the findings contribute to a comparative understanding of post-pandemic dynamics and will inform the subsequent phases of the project, including expert-based Delphi surveys and case study development. They also offer policy-relevant insights by challenging dominant assumptions about formalization and proposing alternative economic imaginaries rooted in lived experience.

2. Methodological Note on Data Collection and Processing

This report follows the common research protocol defined by the PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning (HS) framework. While qualitative and interpretive in orientation, the exercise also followed a structured approach to ensure cross-country comparability. The data collection process was based on the identification and use of pre-defined keywords related to informality, economic recovery, and resilience. In line with the shared methodological guidelines, the research drew on approximately 150 sources, comprising, where available, 50 academic references, 50 media articles, and 50 grey literature or policy documents. These materials were selected through targeted searches, curated for relevance, and then closely read, coded, and interpreted in light of the researcher’s contextual knowledge and disciplinary perspective. Each step of this process keyword selection, source collection, critical reading, and report drafting is made explicit to reinforce methodological transparency. Although the emphasis in this Kenyan case is on qualitative synthesis, the report remains anchored in a systematic data-gathering process shared across the PRESILIENT network. This contributes to a robust and comprehensive report that stands on its own, aligned with the project’s collective aims and epistemological commitments.

3. Informal Economies in Kenya: Socioeconomic Context

The COVID-19 pandemic posed profound challenges to Kenya's economy, impacting key indicators of the economy such as GDP, labor markets, trade, the informal economy, gender dynamics, and marginalized urban populations. The GDP in 2020 shrank to 1.1% from 5.7% (Siringi, 2021). The percentage of the population who experienced a major financial shock in the past year rose from 36% in 2019 to 67% in 2021. The most prevalent shock was the rising cost of living (Amrik, 2022). The labor market faced significant challenges, with widespread job losses, stagnant wages, and increased

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poverty rates, especially in urban areas. Payroll taxes fell below targets, indicative of a tough job market. The gap between rising living costs and stagnant minimum wages worsened the situation, leaving a large portion of the population in poverty. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Kenya's economy experienced significant setbacks as trade disruptions resulted in a decline in GDP, diminished foreign exchange reserves, and depreciation of the currency. Within the East African Community (EAC), both exports and imports sharply declined, impacting key sectors such as industrial supplies and tourism.

The informal sector, which accounts for a substantial portion of employment, faced heightened challenges, including limited access to credit and inadequate social security coverage. Border closures and travel restrictions disrupted informal sector activities, leading to further job losses and income reduction (Donovan, 2020; Fofana & Omolo, 2023; Joshi et al., 2022; Munda, 2023; World Bank, 2021). In Kenya, the Government's economic and social insurance measures aimed at alleviating the crisis predominantly overlooked the informal sector, which encompasses 11.8 million workers and represents 83.6% of the labor force, as per the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics Economic Survey of 2019.

Additionally, the pandemic exacerbated existing gender disparities, particularly affecting women in the workforce. Women-led businesses encountered disproportionate challenges and received less public support. The Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) household survey found that 51.2 percent of women had been rendered jobless due to the pandemic. The increased care burden on women exacerbated gender gaps in employment and income (Suubi et al., 2022).

Moreover, the pandemic worsened pre-existing structural inequalities and health outcomes among marginalized urban populations, such as sex worker communities and the population living in informal settlements in Nairobi (Hassan, Sanders, et al., 2023; Kimani et al., 2020). The lack of government support during the pandemic eroded trust in public institutions, particularly among marginalized residents. Overall, these sectors experienced marginal decreases from the pre-COVID situation, highlighting the severity of the economic impact of the pandemic on Kenya.

4. Regional and Global Comparison

When comparing Kenya informal economy with other countries in Africa, a similar pattern emerges. Nations like Zambia and Morocco also exhibit strong attention to health and marginalization, as well as social protection, reflecting shared challenges around vulnerable populations and healthcare access.

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However, unlike several African countries, Kenya stands out for its relatively higher focus on online marketplaces and tourism impact, which points to its strong integration of mobile money in daily transactions and the importance of tourism to its economy; both of which were significantly affected by the COVID crisis. In contrast, issues such as waste management and urban settlement receive less attention in Kenya than in countries like Zambia, where urbanization pressures and environmental concerns are more prominent.

Globally, Kenya shares key similarities with Thailand and Indonesia, particularly in the high visibility of COVID-related topics, digital economy adoption, and tourism disruption. These countries have also experienced rapid shifts in digital financial services. Yet, Kenya's innovation in mobile money and informal digital transactions, such as M-Pesa, often surpasses that of many Asian and Latin American peers. For instance, while Bolivia and Colombia also prioritized COVID and social protection, Kenya's informal sector has shown more dynamic adaptation through hybrid financial practices. On the other hand, in areas like waste management and urban development, countries such as Thailand have advanced further, suggesting that Kenya may still be focusing its policy and research priorities on immediate economic recovery and inclusion

5. Emerging Trends and Feedback

The COVID-19 crisis triggered significant shifts in various sectors of the Kenyan economy, leading to notable increases in certain areas. One such sector that experienced a boom was mobile digital platforms, as individuals, businesses, and governments increasingly relied on these platforms to reduce financial costs and mitigate the risk of spreading the virus. This trend was particularly evident in the surge of mobile money transactions, which climbed to 208.6 million in August from 184.8 million deals in a similar period the previous year. The rise in transactions indicated the heightened utilization of mobile money for handling lower transaction values, highlighting the adaptability and resilience of digital finance in response to the pandemic (Cowling, 2023; Doyle, 2021; Muiruri, 2023). Furthermore, the government's focus on human capital development, manifested through increased investment in education and training, contributed to the growth of this sector. As governments worldwide responded to the COVID-19 crisis with lockdowns and restrictions on economic activities, there was an increased need for contactless financial products and services. This demand accelerated the shift to digital finance, expanding inclusive access to financial services and driving growth in the digital payments sector (Mugema, 2020; Muiruri, 2023).

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Moreover, initiatives such as the COVID-19 Cash Transfer (CT) program, implemented by a consortium led by GiveDirectly, facilitated the distribution of monthly stipends using mobile money transfers. Although implemented outside the Government of Kenya's systems, such programs played a crucial role in providing financial support to vulnerable populations during the crisis (Omolo, 2020; Siringi, 2021). Additionally, farmers were less likely to experience worsened food security compared to other groups heavily reliant on market sources for food. This resilience may be attributed to the agricultural sector's inherent adaptability and the relatively lower dependence on external markets for sustenance (Kansiime et al., 2021; Shehryar, 2023).

Despite these positive developments, the COVID-19 crisis also underscored persistent challenges, particularly regarding gender equality. The pandemic posed formidable obstacles to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 5, which aims to attain gender equality and empower all women and girls by eliminating all forms of violence against them. Addressing these challenges will be crucial in ensuring a more inclusive and resilient post-pandemic recovery.

6. Related Outputs and Publications

This national report is part of the broader Horizon Scanning (HS) exercise developed within the PRESILIENT project. The following outputs have been produced from this collective research:

- Molina, J. L., Pulgar Corrotea, M., Polese, A., Fradejas-García, I., Ianole-Călin, R., Isaev, A., Mengato, S., Nguyen, M., Carracedo, D., De Lombaerde, G., Avesani, M., Sasikornwong, N., Gambardella, M., Andrias, B., Massera, M., Lima, J. P., Cisagara, B., Rahman, A., Kabaghe, W., & D'Urso, D. (2024). *PRESILIENT Horizon Scanning Dataset [Data set]*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14285318>

This dataset is the consolidated output of the Horizon Scanning research conducted across 15 countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. It comprises three corpora of references: academic literature, media articles, and grey literature sources, gathered and curated to explore economic transformations during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on informal economies.

- Fradejas García, I., Pulgar, M., Molina, J. L., Ianole-Călin, R., & Polese, A. (2024). *Volatility, growth, decline and sustainability perspective of domestic economic sectors after the pandemic: A comparative Horizon Scanning of 15 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273561>

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This comparative publication presents the aggregate results of the Horizon Scanning exercise conducted in 15 countries. Using a keyword-based supervised topic detection method across the combined corpora, it provides an overview of post-pandemic trends, highlighting convergences and divergences among countries and across types of sources. It also discusses patterns of economic volatility, recovery, and the sustainability of growth trajectories in the informal sector.

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